

D9.5: Innovation Management Plan

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ABSTRACT:	The aim of this deliverable is to ensure an appropriate innovation management during the execution of the XR4HUMAN project. This document is an internal guideline for all consortium participants. In addition to the guide, an Excel tool will be used for the identification, listing, categorization, and exploitation strategy of each intellectual asset that is created during the project. The final innovation management report will be a revised version of this document. It will summarise the foreground IP generated and the exploitation plan for each IP to allow maximal exploitation and impact.
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Consortium:

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1 Introduction

1.1 Innovation and innovation management

It is important to have a common understanding in the project about the meaning of innovation. Innovation in this document is based on the definition of innovation by the Oslo manual 2018²: *New or improved product or process (or combination thereof) that differs significantly from the unit's previous products or processes and that has been made available to potential users (product) or brought into use by the unit (process).*

From this perspective, innovation offers new solutions to problems and responds to the needs of both the individual and society. Some of the key factors that create a need for innovation are lack of proper solutions for existing problems in society, changes in customer behaviour, methodological and technological advances, intensified competition, and the changing business environment.

Innovation processes in research and innovation projects usually consist of activities that support the generation of new theories, results, solutions, and ideas as well as the way that this new knowledge or theory is handled, and which steps are necessary to make sure that society benefits from the results.

During a research or/and innovation project, most likely several results will arise that may have a potential value to society or/and market. Innovation Management will efficiently identify, monitor and control the results, as well as overwatch the related society/market needs throughout the project's lifetime. It will also make sure that future activities are adjusted as needed to implement the project's results in such a way that they best meet the needs of the society/market with the results available at the time. In other words, Innovation Management in a research or innovation project is the identification and monitoring of new results during the project that have the potential to become innovations, and to create a strategy for the way towards value for society. The steps included in the strategy might for example include the identification of new project partners to further develop the new result, steps necessary to implement new teaching methods, or it could mean that results should be protected by Creative Commons¹, design protection² or a patent application³. The steps that need to be taken are specific for each result. EU aims to maximize the projects outcome and impact by optimally exploiting the innovations created inside cooperative projects. One way to improve the outcome is to be aware at all times of new innovations being generated inside the project.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

The aim of this deliverable is to describe the innovation management plan of the XR4HUMAN project. It is intended to serve as an internal guideline for the appropriate innovation management of the XR4HUMAN project for all consortium participants.

¹ <https://creativecommons.org/>

² <https://www.patentstyret.no/en/services/designs/>

³ <https://www.patentstyret.no/en/services/patents>

2 Framework and regulations

To create an appropriate innovation management plan, it is important to take into account the aim of the call, the aims of the project and the documents that control the execution of the project (Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement), see descriptions below.

2.1 Call

Type of action: HORIZON Coordination and Support Actions
Call: A HUMAN-CENTRED AND ETHICAL DEVELOPMENT OF DIGITAL AND INDUSTRIAL TECHNOLOGIES 2021 (HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01) and topic: HORIZON-CL4-2021-HUMAN-01-28

The aim of this program is to support the following Key Strategic Orientation:

Creating a more resilient, inclusive, and democratic European society, prepared and responsive to threats and disasters, addressing inequalities and providing high-quality health care, and empowering all citizens to act in the green and digital transitions (KSO D)

Furthermore, it shall contribute to the following expected impact:
A human-centred and ethical development of digital and industrial technologies, through a two-way engagement in the development of technologies, empowering end-users, and workers, and supporting social innovation.

2.2 XR4HUMAN project

XR4HUMAN will, through a strong quadruple-helix of industry-consumers-regulators-academia interaction, generate European standards for XR that will help accelerate an ethical and human-centred development process for hardware and software manufacturers, thereby benefitting technically and commercially from highly usable and inclusive systems. XR4HUMAN also supports end-user decision-making and, through our focus on inclusivity, ensure that every European company and citizen has the potential to take advantage of what XR can offer, paving the way towards a strong and competitive ecosystem whilst building public trust and acceptance, led by European companies in the wider deployment, adoption, and acceptance of XR technologies.

2.3 Grant agreement

The Grant Agreement Article 16 regulates the Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), background and results, access rights and rights of use.

The general rule is that Background knowledge must be shared if it is needed for the implementation of the action.

Annex 5 contains the specific clauses on regulation of the IPR on the results created in the project. In short, the main points here include:

- Ownership to results; these are owned by the beneficiaries that generate them.
- Joint ownership: this needs to be agreed upon by a written agreement.
- Exploitation: it is obligated to exploit results directly or indirectly (though transfer or licensing)
- Transfer of results: Ownership of results may be transferred on the condition that it does not affect compliance with the obligations of the Grant Agreement and project agreements, and that the other beneficiaries with access rights are informed at least 45 days in advance.

- Licensing of results: Non-exclusive licences may be granted to third parties against 45 days of notice to the other joint owners, and against fair and reasonable compensation. Exclusive licences may be granted if all other beneficiaries concerned have waived their access rights, and the granting authority has granted approval. The granting authority may object, depending on the call, for example if it is to a legal entity outside EU.
- Access rights: the beneficiaries must grant each other free access to results needed for implementation of their tasks in the project. Access to background and results needed for exploitation of own results is granted under fair and reasonable conditions.

2.4 Consortium Agreement

Furthermore, in the Consortium Agreement (based on DESCA template), the following is stated:

- Use of results in research and education: each of the joint owners shall be entitled to use their jointly owned Results for non-commercial research and teaching activities on a royalty-free basis, and without requiring the prior consent of the other joint owner(s).
- Non-exclusive license: each of the joint owners shall be entitled to otherwise Exploit the jointly owned Results and to grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties (without any right to sub-license) if the other joint owners are given: (a) at least 45 calendar days advance notice; and (b) fair and reasonable compensation.
- The joint owners shall agree on all protection measures and the division of related cost in advance.
- Licences: like Grant Agreement

3 Background and expected results

3.1 Background knowledge

Background knowledge⁴ is *any data, know-how, information, or rights, such as IPRs, that are held by a beneficiary BEFORE they sign the Grant Agreement and are needed to implement the action or exploit the future results.*

A description of the Background knowledge is included in Attachment 1 in the Consortium Agreement. For the XR4HUMAN, only the University of Leeds describes the software (open source, MIT licence) for the development of the VR platform. None of the other partners described any background.

3.2 Expected results (foreground)

Foreground⁵ means *the tangible and intangible results which are generated within a given project, including pieces of information, materials, and knowledge and whether they can be protected. It includes intellectual property rights (e.g., copyrights, industrial designs, patents, plant variety rights), similar forms of protection (e.g., rights for databases) and unprotected know-how (e.g., confidential material).* Results generated outside a project are not foreground.

⁴ [Background in EU-funded projects \(europa.eu\)](https://europea.europa.eu/en/eu-funding/4-background-in-eu-funded-projects)

⁵ [Glossary - F \(europa.eu\)](https://europea.europa.eu/en/eu-funding/5-glossary-f)

The key exploitable results expected in the XR4HUMAN include the following are listed in the project description (table 2.3, and part 2.3 Summary) and in short include:

- European Code of Conduct (CoC) for human-centred XR technologies: a guideline for equitable, inclusive, and human-centred development of XR technologies and applications
- Interoperability Guidance document: Guidelines to supplement industrial procedures and facilitate ethics appraisal of research for XR.
- Permanent European forum: A platform to connect XR stake holders and support interaction towards common language and understanding of XR technology standards.
- Online repository of test cases: A database consisting of good practices, failure cases, test cases of XR applications
- XR rating systems and supporting toolbox of informative materials: Guidelines to support informed decision-making on the purchase and use of an XR technology.

The general principle for this project is that the partners will openly share the project's findings. Therefore, it is expected that all XR4Human deliverables eventually will be public and shared using open licenses. In case of unforeseen IPR (intellectual property rights) issues, the coordinator with the General Assembly will follow the provisions as described in the Grant Agreement and the overarching IPR regulations.

4 Plan for innovation management

4.1 Innovation management monitoring

For the monitoring of innovation during the project an Innovation Management listing tool will be used (attachment 1). By using this check list, the project team examines the potential exploitation pathway for each of the project results (intellectual assets) as they are generated. It is an easy tool to use and urges the project participants to divide the results into categories, to list the next steps and to define the exploitation plan and need for collaboration partners for each asset.

This tool should be filled out during the regular project meetings and be updated *continuously*.

The excel sheet has the following columns:

- ID: the number of the IA (intellectual asset)
- Title: a short description of the result
- Acronym: if needed, a short name can be defined here
- Short description of possible value: what could this result lead to, what impact could it have, what product or service could it contribute to?
- Category, choose between:
 - o Idea: an overall idea, not (yet) supported by data
 - o Technical solution; solutions to technical problems (methods and processes, devices, compositions, designs, configuration, systems)
 - o Software: a computer-implemented collection of data and operations, performing specified tasks (platforms, programs, applications, drivers, algorithms, and scripts)
 - o Database: Data that are collected in a systemic way (electronic database, matrices)
 - o Results: outcomes from research not falling under the other categories
 - o Instruction: Instructions to execute a specific technical operation (routines, procedures, guidelines, manuals, Standard Operation Procedures, recipes, recommendations)
 - o Observation: conclusions derived from analysing data (trends, optimizations,

- cause/effect, connections)
- Inventors and contributors
- Possible patentable invention yes/no
- Level of secrecy (published or not)
- Documentation (link to documents)
- Steps needed for value creation
- Partners needed for realization

4.2 Final report

At the end of the project the Innovation Management plan will be written in a final form including a summary, introduction, and conclusion, attached with an exploitation strategy and dissemination strategy for each result in form of a table.